

Deliverable D3.2

Tutorial and webinar on Maturity Level Model for Genomics in Healthcare (Month 10)

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1. Executive Summary

The Beyond 1 Million Genomes Plus (B1MGplus) project aims to contribute to the creation of a European cross-border network for genomic and corresponding clinical data access, to promote research and also to improve healthcare outcomes.

The *Webinar and Tutorial on the Maturity Level Model for Genomics in Healthcare* was developed in the context of the B1MGplus Work Package 3, which focuses on healthcare implementation and health economics of genomic medicine, and specifically in Task 3.2 which addresses the adoption of genomics in healthcare by leveraging the *Maturity Level Model (MLM) for Genomics in Healthcare*. In this context, the webinar was created with two main purposes: (1) to disseminate the *MLM for Genomics in Healthcare* and reach a broader audience, namely in countries that might be interested on using this tool in their healthcare systems for assessing the maturity of genomic medicine implementation in health systems; and (2) to provide a detailed demonstration of how to apply the MLM, including potential challenges and strategies to overcome them.

To enable the maximum number of participants, the webinar was held online at 14h (GMT+1). It included a brief explanation on how the MLM was developed; a detailed exposition on how to use it, with practical examples; and information on how countries can compare their results through a benchmarking tool.

Stakeholders from the B1MGplus, Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) and Genome of Europe (GoE) projects, as well as country representatives of the National Mirror Groups of the 1 Million Genomes (1+MG) initiative and members of the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed) were invited. In addition, representatives from countries that had previously expressed interest in the *MLM for Genomics in Healthcare*, as well as those potentially unfamiliar with the tool but likely to be interested, were also invited. Overall, 200 plus invitations were sent by email. This webinar was also disseminated in the GDI Assembly that took place in Copenhagen (Denmark) on 9th September. The dissemination resulted in 159 registrants and 83 attendees on the 25th of September. The audience was diverse, including healthcare professionals, data scientists, public health specialists, economists, bioinformaticians, amongst others, as we believe that all these stakeholders play a crucial role in implementing genomics in healthcare and can provide valuable insights to help maximize its potential. The attendees were also geographically diverse, stemming from countries including Denmark, France, Belgium, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, Brazil, Costa Rica and other Southern American countries. The heterogeneity in origin country and expertise clearly demonstrates the broad value of this framework. The webinar lasted approximately one hour, including a Q&A session. After two months the webinar has attracted 164 views on YouTube, indicating that the content is resonating with stakeholders, and that the webinar is performing well in terms of outreach. A more

complete evaluation of the webinar utility will take longer, as it will require the assessment of indicators like new users of the *MLM for Genomics in Healthcare*.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

Outcome 1		Contributed
Supporting the Genome EDIC WG and the 1+MG Member States on the establishment of the EDIC by carrying out the field work required to generate high quality landscape and scoping documents necessary for the compliance framework beyond the legal creation of an EDIC. These documents will drive EDIC to become operational and offer compliant access to health and genomic data, covering legal, policy, quality and security aspects of data provision.	1. A record of processing activities that captures the legitimacy of EDIC and the corresponding safeguards	No
	2. A number of documents that can be fed back to the GDI Pillar I and/or the EDIC for discussion and/or adoption to provide legal tools and policies to govern the operations for suitable and specific safeguards to ensure the protection of the rights and freedoms of the data subjects whose data are included in the EDIC for secondary use.	No
	3. A framework that can guide the implementation of national IT infrastructure to ensure the quality and the security of workflows, tools and platforms.	No
Outcome 2		Contributed
WP2 will analyse the EHDS Regulation and will seek close exchange with relevant projects and stakeholders to investigate the conditions for a participation in the HealthData@EU infrastructure, to give recommendations on the alignment of its policies, tools, security measures and IT framework with the requirements of the EHDS.	1. An analysis of the model how the EDIC could join the EHDS, its relationship with the various stakeholders and the conditions and opportunities of such participation	No
	2. Information on the practical consequences of the participation in the HealthData@EU infrastructure	No
	3. Engaging public health professionals, and policy makers, in the discussion of benefits and challenges of adopting genomics in healthcare systems for clinical practice and public health policies	No

	4. Documenting the implementation of genomic medicine practices in national healthcare systems	No
	5. Promoting the awareness, literacy level and education of citizens on genomic medicine across Europe.	No
Outcome 3		Contributed
<p>WP3 will provide a framework of reference for genomics in healthcare that supports the decision making process, facilitating the definition of mid and long term targets and the path for genomics implementation, incorporating the feedback received from B1MG and the 1+MG experts.</p>	1. Mapping of gaps, challenges, unmet needs and solutions from the perspective of public health and healthcare professionals, healthcare systems and national genomic healthcare implementation programmes	Yes
	2. Recommendations for the EDIC on the uptake and implementation of genomics for healthcare and public health	Yes
	3. A citizen's hub for dissemination of genomic medicine, promoting citizens and patients awareness, literacy and trust	No
Outcome 4		Contributed
<p>The project will map existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to whole genome sequencing and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare. Building on the collected best practices, and together with experts in the field, the project will develop decision trees to be tested in national settings to guide decision making related to genomics in healthcare. The long term impact of the work is the scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare to support future prioritisation in healthcare, policy makers and decisions on investment in genomic medicine.</p>	1. Overview of literature and existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to WGS and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare	No
	2. Decision trees tested in national settings	No
	3. Scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare	No
Outcome 5		Contributed

Enhancing the 1+MG MLM for the implementation of genomics medicine in healthcare systems with updated domains and indicators, promoting its use and benchmarking by more healthcare systems. This will provide an homogeneous assessment framework that will foster the alignment of optimisation aims in healthcare systems across Europe, closing gaps, reducing asymmetries and ensuring a path towards equity of access to personalised medicine for all Europeans.	1. Updated 1+MG MLM incorporating novel dimensions aligned with emerging developments in genomic medicine	No
	2. Benchmarking of the MLM by healthcare systems across Europe	Yes
Outcome 6		Contributed
Expand the 1+MG Framework to fully define the 1+MG minimal metadata model, data standards, ontologies and quality criteria providing accessibility and maintenance, ensuring continuous alignment and support of 1+MG data use for research, innovation and policy making.	1. Phenotype data model	No
	2. Genotype data model	No
	3. Terms of use/ELSI metadata	No
	4. Software quality indicators for components to be incorporated into the 1+MG journey.	No
	5. Data/metadata provenance models	No

3. Aims

The aims of the *Webinar and Tutorial on the Maturity Level Model for Genomics in Healthcare* were:

- To disseminate the MLM for Genomics in Healthcare and reach experts from countries that might potentially be interested in using this tool to assess the maturity level of the healthcare system regarding the implementation of genomic medicine
- To provide practical guidance on how to use the MLM for Genomics in Healthcare, including potential challenges and how to overcome them.

4. Methods

The presentation for the webinar was prepared in Microsoft Power Point and included videos demonstrating how to use specific features of the MLM for genomics in healthcare with practical examples, namely the assessment tool and the user guide[1]. The session was hosted in the Zoom platform using the webinar mode that allowed a better control over the course of the webinar and access specific features important for this format, such as higher number of participations and meeting duration.

The webinar was presented by Astrid Vicente, with Maria Luís Cardoso and Marta Moniz as supporting team. Their primary role was to ensure the session ran smoothly and on schedule, as well as to manage the Q&A chat. An IT support representative was also present to handle all technical aspects. A test session was conducted one week prior to the webinar to ensure the platform was functioning properly, the presentation flowed smoothly, the access link worked correctly, and check all technical elements were in place which was particularly important, as the webinar was recorded to make it available for later access.

The webinar comprehended a brief explanation on the development process of the MLM for Genomics in Healthcare[2]; followed by an in-depth demonstration of its applications and a presentation on how countries can benchmark their results derived from the MLM. The outcomes of a pilot of the MLM in eight European countries was also presented. To ensure broad participation, the session was held online at 14h (GMT+1).

The list of invitees was based on stakeholders who might be interested in participating and/or disseminating the activity. The invitations were sent to the 1Million Genomes (1+MG) WG6 and WG7 National Mirror Groups, B1MGplus participants, GDI and GoE stakeholders mailing lists; representatives from countries that had previously expressed interest in the MLM; ICPeMed; Public Policy Projects Forum; Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH); Latin America stakeholders through the President of the Human Genetics Network were also invited. Over 200 contacts were invited. The registration form was created using Microsoft Forms, and a link was sent to all invitees. Afterwards, those who registered received a separate link to join the webinar. The recorded webinar was made available on the B1MGplus website and on INSA's official YouTube channel. The access link was subsequently shared with all invitees, allowing those who were unable to attend to watch the session and refer back to it if they needed to clarify any details.

Slido, an interactive tool[3] was used to collect real time input from participants on specific topics and to foster engagement with the audience. This method tool allowed the audience to share their thoughts anonymously and visually, enhancing participation, gathering opinions and helping to guide the flow of the session. Three questions were presented: two word-clouds prompts, *“What would be the main challenges to use this MLM to assess the healthcare systems in your country/region?”* and *“What key indicators could be added?”* and

one rating scale question presented as a bar graph, “How useful do you find the Benchmarking Tool?”.

5. Results and work accomplished

From the over 200 invitations sent, 159 participants registered for the webinar and 83 finally attended. From the 23 countries represented, Portugal, Spain, France and Belgium had the highest attendance (Figure 1). The diversity of attendees demonstrated the wide appeal of the *MLM for Genomics in Healthcare*, attracting interest from a range of professionals, with genetics and genomics, public health and laboratory sciences being the most highly represented areas of expertise (Figure 2). The participants represented a broad spectrum of roles, from clinicians and senior leaders to PhD students, managers, and policy advisors. Such engagement across career stages and sectors underlines that this framework is not only relevant today but will continue shaping the future of research, healthcare and governance in genomics.

Figure 1. Number of attendees by country

Figure 2. Number of attendees by area of expertise

The interactive activity *Slido* revealed valuable insights from the participants. Their answers will be taken into consideration moving forward. “Collaboration between different entities”, “resources to do the assessment” and “awareness” were some of the answers to the question “*What would be the main challenges to use this MLM to assess the healthcare systems in your country/region?*” (Figure 3); to the question “*What key indicators could be added?*” (Figure 4) the participants suggested to include measures of connection between research and healthcare sectors; and address inequities regarding the implementation of genomic medicine, for instance in access to genetic testing or inclusion of genomic information from multiple ancestries including minorities. Noteworthy, one of the participants suggested that the framework was already extensive and that no more domains should be added for the time being, which highlights the versatility of this tool considering the maturity level each country is at. That is, it can either be dynamically adapted to expand the domains or, for others, the existing ones are already sufficient. Over 50% of respondents rated the tool 5 out of 5 (Figure 5). Overall, the audience showed strong interest in the

content presented, which reinforces its importance and relevance. The presentation is available in the project shared folder¹. The record of this webinar is available on the B1MGplus website² and on the official Youtube channel of INSA³. After the webinar, the link was disseminated to over 250 people by email and as of December 3rd 2025, the webinar had 164 views on YouTube.

Figure 3. Word cloud with the participant’s answers to the question “*What would be the main challenges to use this MLM to assess the healthcare systems in your country/region?*”

¹ [Webinar Maturity Level Mode for Genomics in Healthcare](#)

² [B1MGplus webinar highlights the Maturity Level Model for Genomics in Healthcare](#)

³ <https://youtu.be/tfbCPiXYctM>

Figure 4. Word cloud with the participant’s answers to the question “What key indicators could be added?”

Figure 5. Score result from the participant’s answers to the question “How useful do you find the Benchmarking Tool?”

6. Discussion, Conclusions & Impact

The webinar offered a comprehensive and accessible explanation of the MLM, presenting its objectives, methodology and added value in a way that helps shape and enhance countries' understanding. By clarifying key concepts and demonstrating the practical relevance of the MLM, the session has promoted broader dissemination of this tool, enabling the initiative to reach an expanding audience. This increased visibility is expected to stimulate countries' interest and, ultimately, encourage wider participation. Notably, within just two months, the webinar has attracted 164 views on YouTube, a promising indication that the content is resonating with stakeholders and generating tangible progress in terms of visibility and outreach. Over time we will be able to more thoroughly assess the impact of this webinar in terms of the usage of the MLM for Genomics in Healthcare by additional countries.

7. Next steps

The next steps will focus on supporting countries interested in applying the MLM for Genomics in Healthcare. The benchmarking tool will be made publicly available online to facilitate its use and comparison across healthcare systems. In addition, the project team will assess the possibility of adding new indicators based on insights gathered during monthly expert meetings dedicated to the various domains of the MLM. These activities aim to enhance the applicability, relevance and adaptability of the model for diverse national contexts.

8. References

- [1] Lopes F, Costa A, Cardoso ML, et al. 1+MG / B1MG Maturity Level Model (MLM) User Guide n.d. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10066995>.
- [2] Beyond 1 Million Genomes (B1MG) Project. The Beyond 1 Million Genomes (B1MG) Maturity Level Model (MLM) 2020. <https://b1mg-project.eu/resources/maturity-level-model> (accessed October 14, 2025).
- [3] Slido. Slido 2025. <https://www.slido.com/> (accessed September 1, 2025).

